

A STUDY TO ASSESS LEVEL OF ANXIETY AND STRESS AMONG THE SELECTED COLLEGE STUDENTS REGARDING UNIVERSITY EXAM DURING THE PERIOD OF EXAMINATION

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ABSTRACT:-

The relationship between stress and anxiety is complicated. Stress initially arises from one's environment; anxiety overlays physiological arousal, cognitive appraisals, emotional states, and behavioral responses. Both are components of a stress-anxiety complex, which has evolved to enable individuals to adapt to their environment and achieve equilibrium. Anxiety disorders, which result when this mechanism goes awry, occur along a spectrum. One of the main variables affecting anxiety disorders is the extent of stress. Each anxiety disorder should be evaluated along a stress axis, leading to improved case conceptualization and intervention strategies. A descriptive study design was used to assess anxiety and stress level among the college going student the data was collected from 50 students selected by non-probability purposive sampling technique by using structured questionnaire

Findings in relation to socio demographic data of students revealed that , 30% had 19 years, 56% were males, 84% were Hindu, 84% were stay in hostel, 92% were had science stream 98% were had no habits, 74% were had nuclear family, 52% were live in rural area and 42% were got 70-80% in Hsc.

Assessment of the anxiety and stress of nursing students regarding university examination revealed that 78% and 88% student had a moderate level of anxiety and stress respectively. The overall mean anxiety score was 24.67 with the standard deviation of 9.21and, The overall mean stress score was 60.92 with the standard deviation of 18.19 .There was significant the association between the anxiety and stress among the selected college student regarding university examination with demographic variable ($T= 3.84$, $P \leq 0.05$) hence null hypothesis rejected.

(Keyword – Anxiety, Stress, Nursing student, University examination.)

1. INTRODUCTION

Everyone goes through anxiety and stress at one time or another. Stress and anxiety goes hand in hand as anxiety is a response to the stress in times of threat. Anxiety is a vague feeling of dread that is Unwarranted by the situation or any event. It is an unpleasant affect characterized by psychological, Physiological and behavioural changes in response to an intra psychic conflict. Nursing course is very stressful, most of the students experience increase stress prior to their class adjustment because of ragging from their seniors, clinical rotations or their written examinations, especially their finals. More paperwork and skill performance and evaluation system increase the tension round the year with very tight schedule. Academic sources of stress include long hours of study during examination assignments and grades, lack of free time, and lack of timely feedback when stress is perceived negatively or becomes excessive, students experience physical and psychological impairment. Methods to reduce stress by students often include effective time management, social support, positive reappraisal and engagement in leisure activities.

Anxiety may place nursing students at risk for being unsuccessful in their programs due to their inability to demonstrate their knowledge base. Poor performance in a course can lead to increased pressure on oneself, especially if the outcome of a test or of a course is very important. A single experience of extreme anxiety can leave a student uncertain if it will occur again and it will affect attrition rates of nursing students across the country, compounding the problem of nursing shortages.³

2. METODOLOGY

Research methodology is a way by which research problem are systematically solved. It may be understood as all those methods or techniques that are used for conducting a research. A research methodology defines what are the activity of research is, how to measure the progress, and what constitute success. Methodology of research indicates the general pattern for organizing the process for the empirical study together with the method of obtaining valid and reliable data for an investigation. This chapter deals with the methodology adopted A descriptive study to assess level of anxiety and stress of among the selected college students regarding university exam during the period of examination. It includes the description of the research approach, research design and setting of the study; samples, sampling techniques, development of data collection tool, procedure for data collection and plan for data analysis.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This chapter deals with the analysis and interpretation of the data collected from the students in a selected college in selected area. Analysis is a process of organizing and synthesizing data in such a way that research questions can be answered and hypothesis tested. The data obtained were analysed and interpreted in the light of objectives and the hypothesis of the study. The collected data were tabulated in a master data sheet and analysed by using descriptive and inferential statistics.

OBJECTIVES

PRIMARY OBJECTIVE:-

1. To assess the anxiety and stress level of the college students, regarding university exam

SECONDARY OBJECTIVE:-

2. To find out the association between anxiety and stress level of the college students regarding the university exam with selected demographic variable

PRESENTATION OF DATA

To begin with, the data was entered in a master sheet, for tabulation and statistical processing. To find the relationship, the data were tabulated, analysed, and interpreted by using descriptive and inferential statistics.

The data is presented under the following headings.

Section-A: Analysis of demographic data

Section-B: Analysis of anxiety and stress among the selected nursing students regarding university examination.

Section-C: Association between anxiety and stress among the selected nursing students regarding university examination.

Section-A: Analysis of demographic data

Total 50 students had participated in this study baseline data reveal that 84% student belong to Hindu religion , 8% belongs to Muslim religion , 8% student belongs to Christian religion .majority of student belongs to Hindu religion about 84% students belongs to hostel and 16%

belongs to home so interpreted that majority of student belongs to hostel. 92% of students belongs to science, 4% belongs to arts and 4% of students belongs to commerce. Hence it can be interpreted that majority of the students belongs to science stream. student according to their habits shows about 98% students belongs to none category and 2% belongs to alcohol so interpreted that majority of student belongs to none category. type of family a shows about 74% students belongs to nuclear family and 26% belongs to join family so interpreted that majority of student belongs to nuclear family. About 48% students belongs to urban area and 52% belongs to rural area so interpreted that majority of student belongs to urban area

Section-B: Analysis of anxiety and stress among the selected nursing students regarding university examination.

Anxiety Score Of Mean And SD During University Examination Among First Year

SR NO	ANXIETY	MAXIMUM SCORE	MEAN	SD
1	Academic	20	11.5	3.11
2	Interpersonal	20	9.86	2.79
3	Intrapersonal	20	3.31	3.31
TOTAL		60	24.67	9.21

B.Sc Nursing Students

INERPRETATION:

In order to assess anxiety among the selected college student regarding university examination maximum score of anxiety is 60. Mean is 24.67 and Standard deviation is 9.21

**Stress Score Of Mean And SD During University Examination Among First Year
B.Sc Nursing Students**

Sr.No.	Stress Area	Maximum Score	Mean	SD
1	Academic stressors	20	10.52	3.03
2	Interpersonal stressors	20	10.96	3.18
3	Intrapersonal stressors	20	10.92	3.25
4	Time balance stressors	20	10.08	3.03
5	Family stressors	20	9.12	2.81
6	Environmental stressors	20	9.32	2.89
TOTAL		120	60.92	18.19

INTERPRETATION:

In order to assess stress among the selected college student regarding university examination above table shows maximum score of anxiety is 120, Mean is 60.92 and Standard deviation is 18.19.

Section -C: Association of anxiety and stress of nursing student regarding university examination.

Sr.No.	Demographic Variables	X ²	Level Of Signicant
1.	Age	3.66	Not-Significant
2.	Sex	2.55	Not-Significant
3.	Religion	1.77	Not-Significant
4.	Accommodation	3.61	Not-Significant
5.	Stream	4.78	Significant*
6.	Habit	5.86	Significant*
7.	Type of family	5.77	Significant*
8.	Place of residence	4.07	Significant*
9.	Percentage of higher secondary	5.93	Significant*

(df-1, Table-3.84, P ≤0.05)

Chi square value find out to find association between stress and anxiety Depicted that association between level of anxiety and stress with their selected demographic variables show that there will be significant association between anxiety and stress level with their selected demographic variables Like steam Habit, Type of family, place of Residence & percentage of higher secondary hence the result show null hypotheses rejected & Alternative hypotheses accepted there is no significant association between anxiety and stress with their selected demographic variable.

CONCLUSION

The following conclusion have been drawn by keeping the findings of the present study in the mind Assessment of the anxiety and stress of nursing students regarding university examination revealed that 78% and 88% student had a moderate level of anxiety and stress respectively.

The overall mean anxiety score was (24.67) with the standard deviation of (9.21) and, the overall mean stress score was (60.92) with the standard deviation of (18.19).

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